

Strategic Online Search Skills and Job Performance of Academics in Federal Universities, South-South Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the differences in job performance between male and female academics based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. Seven specific objectives were outlined, one research question was raised, and one null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. An ex-post facto research design was adopted. The population comprised 7,107 academics (4,830 male and 2,177 female) from seven federal universities across the six South-South states during the 2022/2023 academic session. The Krejcie and Morgan Sample Size Determination Table and a multi-stage sampling procedure were used to select 1,393 respondents. Two researcher-developed instruments, titled Strategic Online Search Skills Questionnaire (SOSSA) and Job Performance of Academics Questionnaire (JPAQ), were used for data collection. Face validation was conducted by three research experts, and Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients of 0.86 and 0.80 were obtained for the SOSSA and JPAQ, respectively. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to test the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed significant differences in job performance between male and female academics in federal universities in South-South Nigeria based on their strategic online search skills. The study recommended, among other things, that efforts should be made by the federal government to minimise the challenges faced by female academics in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. Furthermore, universities should provide gender-sensitive training on strategic online search skills to ensure equitable benefits for all academics.

Keywords: Strategic Online Search Skills, Job Performance, Academics, Federal Universities

Introduction

The emergence of information communication technologies (ICT) has remarkably affected almost every sphere of life. With ICT, educational products are marketed, schools are advertised, messages are sent and received within seconds, reading materials are uploaded and downloaded for several activities like conferences, workshops, and seminars, and educational settings are being transformed to where educators are expected to teach and learn using it.

The goal of information and communication technology in education, as enshrined in the National Policy on Information and Communication Technology in Education (2019), is to meet the human capital requirements of the nation for attaining and

enhancing sustainable socio-economic development and global competitiveness, as well as the individual's ability to survive in a contemporary environment using ICT. The objectives of ICT in education are to:

- a. facilitate the teaching and learning processes.
- b. promote problem-solving, critical thinking and innovative skills.
- c. promote life-long learning and advance knowledge.
- d. enhance the various teaching/learning strategies required to meet the needs of the population.
- e. foster research and development.
- f. support effective and efficient education administration.
- g. enhance universal access to information.
- h. widen access to education, range of instructional options and opportunities for any-where, any-time, any-pace and any-path learning, and
- i. promote the commercialization of indigenous inventions, products and services of ICT in education.

In the university, academics are known for teaching, research and community service. Academics, male or female, make use of ICT for their service delivery (otherwise known as job performance), especially in teaching and research. Performance is the measurement of actual output or result against set goals. Job performance is the degree to which an academic or scholar can effectively combine duties (such as teaching, research and community service) (Mbon *et al.*, 2019; Odigwe *et al.*, 2020; Owan *et al.*, 2020). It is the measure of the effectiveness of academics in relation to their roles and responsibilities in their workplace. Taiwo (2014) opined that job performance is the overall expected value from employees' behaviours carried out over the course of a set period of time. Okoi and Odigwe (2018) explained that academic staff job performance is the association between teaching features and educational success in the classroom. It could therefore be deduced that academics' performances in the universities are basically measured by their research output, quality of teaching and community services. However, job performance is delimited to teaching and research in this study. Academics are expected to administer continuous assessment in the form of class tests and take-home assignments and supervise students in their research works. They are also expected to write journal articles and attend national and international conferences, seminars and workshops. Online search skills are always on hand to enhance efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out these activities. This could help them meet their job demands and engender positive work life.

Online search skills allow quicker access to study materials through the internet. The use of online search to access journals, periodicals, magazines, inaugural lectures, and conference papers could help a lecturer to grow fast on the job and in the long run; the stress that comes with teaching and research work is reduced minimally. In their service delivery, it appears that many perform their jobs effectively while some do not. Some find it difficult to update knowledge in their respective areas of specialisation. This could

possibly be influenced by one's knowledge of the online search skills, especially the strategic online search skills. Strategic online search skill is the user's capacity to design and adapt search strategies purposefully to achieve specific information goals in the incorporation of proactive decision-making, flexibility and iterative refinement of search engines. It refers to an online user's ability to plan, adapt, and optimise search strategies to efficiently locate high-quality information. Nwabueze (2022) opined that strategic skill is the ability to structure search questions using the appropriate rules, such as words, signs and punctuation, to make an understandable phrase that is easily recognised by the database and search engine to get precise results from numerous online resources. Dijk (2015) defines strategic skill as the capacity to use computers and network sources as the means for particular goals and for the general goal of improving one's position in society. In other words, strategic skill includes the capacity to use the Internet to attain particular goals, as well as the ability to attain the general goal of improving one's position in society.

Strategic online search skills could play an important role in the job performance of academics in the universities. It is arguable that some individuals experience difficulties in customising search terms, reasoning with the search results, having a critical attitude towards the resource, and organising the search process. Some argue that males are more likely than females to struggle with strategic online search skills. Large *et al.* (2002) revealed that boys and girls around age 11 differ in the way they search for information. Boys, for example, used only one keyword more often than girls, who combined multiple keywords. Furthermore, boys tended to click links more often and stayed on a page for shorter periods of time than did girls. These differences, however, do not result in large differences in the actual results. In contrast, Hargittai and Shafer (2006), Deursen and Dijk (2011), and Kuhlemeier and Hemker (2007) all conducted actual performance tests that revealed no differences between men and women.

From the foregoing, it appears the evidence for specific gender differences in strategic online search skill and its effect on job performance is inconclusive, although there is a widespread belief that computers and the internet are male-dominated technologies. Therefore, there is a need to examine the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. The question, therefore, is what is the difference in male and female academics' job performance based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria?

Statement of the Problem

The job performance of academics is critical to the advancement of knowledge, the quality of education, and the overall effectiveness of academic institutions. However, numerous factors can impede their performance, including challenges related to research productivity, teaching effectiveness and the ability to engage in professional

development. Moreover, the academic landscape is continuously evolving; today it is driven by technological advancements and changing educational demands; with these, it appears that some academics struggle to navigate the complexities of modern research environments that require not only expertise in their subject matter but also proficiency in digital tools. It appears also that some academics do not prepare adequately for classroom activities; some do not regularly attend seminars, conferences and workshops to enhance their research work. Moreover, some do not have an interest in carrying out research, as they find it difficult to search for relevant information for lectures, conferences, and workshops, among others.

These anomalies could be associated with a lack of strategic online search skills by some academics. This is because strategic online search skills are essential for academics to access, evaluate and utilise information effectively to improve job performance. If this situation is allowed to continue, it may frustrate the objectives and goals for which universities were set up or established. In a bid to solving this problem, the gender disparities that exist in the development and application of these skills have caught many scholars' attention. Some scholars argue that more males acquire more strategic online search skills than the female counterparts, while others argue in favour of the female academics. These differences may influence their ability to locate relevant literature, conduct thorough research and ultimately contribute to their productivity and career advancement. Despite the importance of strategic online search skills in supporting academic work, the difference in job performance of male and female academics due to strategic online search skills is yet to be ascertained. Therefore, this study was designed to find the difference that exists in the job performance of male and female academics based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. The question, therefore, is what is the difference in male and female academics' job performance based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the research question below:

- i. What is the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

This null hypothesis guided the study:

- i. There is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

The study was delimited to strategic online search skills and job performance of academics in federal universities in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study was delimited to academics in all the seven federal universities in the South-South region of Nigeria in the year 2023. The choice of this region emanated from the fact that the researcher is resident in South-South, Nigeria, as well as the proximity between the universities. Also, the job performance of academics was delimited to teaching and research.

Conceptual Framework

Gender, Strategic Online Search Skill and Job Performance of Academics

Strategic skill includes the capacity to use the Internet to attain particular goals, as well as the ability to attain the general goal of improving one's position in society. Strategic skill is the ability to structure search questions using the appropriate rules, such as words, signs and punctuation, to make an understandable phrase that is easily recognised by the database and search engine to get precise results from numerous online resources (Nwabueze 2022). Dijk (2015) defines strategic skill as the capacity to use computers and network sources as the means for particular goals and for the general goal of improving one's position in society. Strategic online search skill explains the gap between those who use technology for professional and educational development and those who mainly use it for entertainment. Strategic online search skills are an advanced subset of digital literacy skills that involve the ability to plan, refine, and adapt search strategies effectively to retrieve specific, high-quality information. Unlike operational skills, which focus on basic navigation, strategic skills are characterised by the thoughtful application of search techniques, iterative refinement, and proactive decision-making to optimise search outcomes (Bilal, 2001). These skills are essential for users who need to navigate vast amounts of information to meet complex goals, such as conducting academic research or engaging in evidence-based practice. With strategic online search skills, academics are able to advance in professional development by taking advantage of the opportunities available online.

Strategic online search skills go beyond the basic mechanics of using search engines. They require a deliberate approach to planning and executing search queries, often involving steps such as:

- Formulating specific and relevant keywords based on the topic or research question.
- Adjusting and refining search queries iteratively based on initial results, which may involve modifying keywords or trying alternative terms.
- Using advanced search operators such as Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT), filters, and domain limitations to improve precision.
- Evaluating search results and deciding on follow-up searches if the retrieved information does not fully meet the need (Tsai & Tsai, 2003; Brand-Gruwel *et al.*, 2005).

Strategic retrieval skill is significant in information retrieval as it assists in the improvement of search skills and online information resources utilisation (Ekenna and

Mabawonku, 2013). Adding more keywords can help you narrow down your results and get very specific pages, but many simple search engines may not interpret those words, or the relationships between them, as you might want. When using three or more keywords, it is often best to use an engine that will allow you to use Boolean logic operators to define the relationship between the words. These are: AND, OR, NOT, NEAR, and parentheses. The procedure begins with goal orientation, followed by engaging in the right actions. Next comes the time to make decisions about how to reach the original goal using selectively retrieved information. The final step is obtaining the benefits of making the optimal decision. Academics in the university need to map out strategies to ascertain the process that would best retrieve the exact information needed for their goal. Knowing what to do and when to do it is fundamental to a successful information search, which would then lead to an increase in their job performance. Ama (2004) explained that some search strategies, such as Boolean logic, truncation and proximity features, are useful for retrieval of information. Search techniques are used to search for information, author or title search from Online Public Catalogue (OPAC), search engines (Google, Yahoo, Ask, Bing, Alta Vista and Google Scholar for online search, etc.). Academic improvement in strategic search skills could speed up the whole information search process and equally contribute to a more effective and comprehensive search and enhance utilisation of online information resources.

Abdulkadir and Mohammed (2020) opined that strategic skills appear to be the most complex of all the types of digital skills distinguished and have never been measured at all. They further explained that taking advantage of the Internet is a process that entails four analytically distinct steps thus.

1. **Goal Orientation:** This means being aware of the opportunities that the web offers and taking advantage of these opportunities for a particular personal or professional goal. Keeping an eye on this goal and acting towards it are difficult and hard-to-learn skills, especially in a digital media landscape that offers an enormous number of distracting stimuli for other goals.
2. **Taking the right actions on the internet:** This means combining the various possible information sources to achieve the best means for the goal desired. After the right actions are taken, it is time to make decisions to reach the original goal by using the (often excessive amount of) information retrieved selectively.
3. **Making decisions:** This involves taking decisions on what site to visit and what search engine to use. This should be done by consulting the right information sources relevant for work, study or personal life.
4. **Gaining The Actual Benefit:** When the right decisions are made, they can be turned into benefits of a personal, social, professional or educational nature.

In academic and professional environments, strategic online search skills are essential for effectively managing information overload and producing high-quality work. Academics, in particular, rely on these skills to conduct comprehensive literature reviews, stay current with research developments, and gather credible sources for their

publications. Those with strong strategic skills are more efficient in retrieving relevant information and can better evaluate the quality of sources, which in turn enhances the rigour of their work (Brand-Gruwel *et al.*, 2009).

A study by Dinet and Kitajima (2011) highlighted that academic researchers who use strategic search methods tend to have more success in identifying and synthesising reliable information, which positively impacts their job performance. Furthermore, Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) emphasise that strategic search skills are essential for lifelong learning, as they allow individuals to remain adaptable and informed in fields where knowledge and technology constantly evolve.

There is evidence that gender is a factor in strategic skills related to Internet usage. Most studies reporting such differences used self-assessments, where women tended to rate their Internet skills as worse than those of men (Deursen and Dijk, 2010) or where girls in secondary schools rated their skills as worse than those of boys (Kuhlemeier and Hemker, 2007). However, Large *et al.* (2002) revealed that boys and girls around age 11 differ in the way they search for information. Boys, for example, used only one keyword more often than girls, who combined multiple keywords. Furthermore, boys tended to click links more often and stayed on a page for shorter periods of time than did girls. These differences, however, do not result in large differences in the actual results. In contrast, Hargittai and Shafer (2006), Deursen and Dijk (2011), and Kuhlemeier and Hemker (2007) all conducted actual performance tests that revealed no differences between men and women. However, when provided with equal access to training, both men and women can develop strong strategic search skills. Gender disparities in these skills often reflect broader social factors rather than inherent ability, highlighting the importance of inclusive digital literacy programs (Cooper, 2006).

Research method

An ex-post facto research design was adopted for this study to examine the differences in job performance between male and female academics based on their strategic online search skills in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. According to Tippins (2023), ex-post facto research, also known as "after-the-fact" research, is a type of research design where the investigation begins after the event has occurred, without any interference from the researcher. This design was deemed appropriate for the study as it allowed the researcher to analyse job performance without directly influencing the behaviour or outcomes of the participants.

The study was conducted in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, which comprises six states: Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers. The population for the study included 7,107 male and female academics from seven federal universities in the region, with 4,830 males and 2,177 females (Nigerian University System Statistical Digest, 2022). The universities under study were University of Uyo, Uyo (1,202 academics), Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun, Delta State (189 academics), Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa (428 academics), Nigerian Maritime University, Okerenkoko, Delta State (100 academics), University of Port Harcourt (1,238 academics), University of Benin (1,896 academics), University of Calabar (2,054 academics).

A sample size of 1,393 participants was drawn from the population of 7,107 academics using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) Sample Size Determination Table. A multi-stage sampling approach was employed, which included stratification, purposive sampling, and simple random sampling.

The Strategic Online Search Skills Questionnaire (SOSSQ) and the Job Performance of Academics Questionnaire (JPAQ) were utilised for data collection. The SOSSA was structured into two sections: Section A, which gathered demographic information such as gender and years of experience, and Section B, which measured strategic online search skills. The instrument consisted of seven items assessing strategic online search skills, presented as declarative statements on a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). Similarly, the JPAQ comprised two clusters, each containing ten items, resulting in a total of 20 items representing key sub-variables of academic job performance. Like the SOSSA, the JPAQ utilised a four-point Likert scale (SA, A, D, SD).

Instrument validity refers to the extent to which an instrument accurately measures what it is intended to measure (Cohen et al., 2011). To establish the validity of the instruments used in this study, the researcher sought expert reviews from three validators: two from the Department of Curriculum Studies and Educational Management and Planning and one from the Measurement and Evaluation Unit in the Department of Psychological Foundations of Education, all within the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The validators assessed the instruments for clarity, appropriateness, and relevance to the study variables and recommended modifications, which were subsequently incorporated.

To determine the internal consistency of the Online Search Skills Questionnaire (OSSQ) and the Job Performance of Academics Questionnaire (JPAQ), an inter-item reliability approach was applied. The instruments **were administered to 50 academics who were not part of the study sample, and the collected data were analysed using Cronbach's Alpha. The results indicated reliability coefficients of 0.86 for the OSSQ and 0.80 for the JPAQ. According to Suhartini et al. (2021), a Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.7 is considered acceptable, confirming the reliability of the instruments for this study.**

The researcher, assisted by five research assistants, collected data from four selected universities using an introductory letter issued by the Department of Curriculum Studies, Educational Management and Planning, University of Uyo, Uyo. Prior to questionnaire distribution, the researcher sought and obtained permission from the respective university authorities. Respondents were assured of strict confidentiality regarding their responses.

To ensure adherence to research protocols, the five research assistants received

comprehensive training on the study's procedures, ethical considerations, and questionnaire content. The distribution and collection of questionnaires spanned six weeks, after which the completed questionnaires were retrieved from the four universities. Of the 1,393 questionnaires distributed, 1,370 were properly completed and returned, comprising 995 male and 375 female respondents, yielding a 98.3% response rate. According to Linderman (2021), a response rate of 57% or higher is considered acceptable for in-person surveys. All valid responses were included in the data analysis.

Mean and standard deviation were used to address the research questions, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The study examined gender-based differences in academic job performance in relation to online search skills among faculty in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. The decision rule for hypothesis testing was to reject the null hypothesis if the calculated F-value exceeded the critical F-value, considering the corresponding p-value at the 0.05 significance level; otherwise, the null hypothesis was retained. Also, online search skills were categorized using the following scale: 1.00–2.49 (Not Acquired), 2.50–4.00 (Acquired).

For the research questions, the higher mean score determined which gender group demonstrated better job performance based on various online search skill dimensions (operational, formal, information, strategic, communication, content creation, and generic online search skills).

Throughout the research process, the researcher adhered to ethical principles and professional standards in educational research. Respondents participated voluntarily and without coercion, ensuring fairness and minimizing stress during data collection. The study was conducted with integrity and in accordance with established ethical guidelines.

Results

Research Question

What is the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on strategic online search skills in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation for the difference in job performance of male and female academics, based on strategic online search skill.

Gender	Strategic Online Search skills	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	Acquired	52.32	18.05	622
	Not Acquired	46.73	16.34	373
	Total	50.22	17.63	995
Female	Acquired	35.26	7.79	268
	Not Acquired	33.78	5.12	107
	Total	34.84	7.15	375
Total	Acquired	47.18	17.53	890
	Not Acquired	43.84	15.57	480
	Total	46.01	16.94	1370

Source: Field Data (2024)

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics on the job performance of male and female academics based on their strategic online search skills. The results indicate the mean and standard deviation values for job performance among academics who acquired and did not acquire strategic online search skills. Specifically, the mean job performance score for male academics who acquired strategic online search skills was 52.32, while those who did not acquire these skills had a mean score of 46.73. Similarly, female academics who acquired strategic online search skills had a mean job performance score of 35.26, whereas those who did not acquire these skills had a mean score of 33.78.

These findings suggest that male academics with strategic online search skills outperformed their female counterparts in terms of job performance in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. Additionally, the standard deviations for male and female academics exceeded 1, with values of 18.05, 16.34, 7.79, and 5.12, respectively. This further indicates variability in job performance scores based on strategic online search skills. Thus, the results confirm that job performance among male and female academics differs significantly based on their level of strategic online search skills acquisition.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on strategic online search skills in Federal Universities in south-south, Nigeria

Table 2: Analysis of Variance of the difference in strategic online search skills of male and female academics based on job performance

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	71913.683	3	23971.228	102.075	.000
Intercept	1626916.657	1	1626916.657	6927.795	.000
Gender	51866.475	1	51866.475	220.860	.000
strategic Online	2878.602	1	2878.602	12.258	.000
Gender * strategic Online	967.674	1	967.674		.043
Error	320790.130	1366	234.839		
Total	3293096.000	1370			
Corrected Total	392703.813	1369			

**significant at .05 alpha level*

The results presented in Table 2 indicate the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) findings regarding the significant difference in job performance between male and female academics based on strategic online search skills. The analysis yielded an F-value of 4.121 with a corresponding significance level of 0.043, based on 1 and 1,366 degrees of freedom. Since the p-value (0.043) is less than the 0.05 significance threshold, the null hypothesis, which posited that there is no significant difference in job performance between male and female academics based on strategic online search skills, is rejected. This result confirms that a significant difference exists in the job performance of male and female academics in federal universities in South-South Nigeria, depending on their level of strategic online search skills acquisition.

Discussion of Findings

Gender, Strategic Online Search Skill and Job Performance of Academics

Findings from research question four revealed that male and female academics in federal universities in South-South Nigeria differ in job performance based on their strategic online search skills. Specifically, the results indicate that male academics possess strategic online search skills more than their female counterparts, which, in turn, influences their job performance. Additionally, data analysis for the hypothesis confirmed a significant difference in job performance between male and female academics based on strategic online search skills. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference in job performance between male and female academics based on strategic online search skills, was rejected.

This result may be attributed to the role of strategic online search skills in bridging the gap between individuals who leverage technology for professional and educational development and those who primarily use it for entertainment. Academics with strong strategic online search skills can enhance their professional growth by effectively utilizing online resources. The findings suggest that male academics were more proficient in defining proper search queries, evaluating retrieved information, maintaining search focus, and taking appropriate steps to achieve their research objectives. They demonstrated a greater ability to use Boolean operators, truncation search techniques, author or title searches in online public access catalogs (OPAC), and

search engines such as Google, Yahoo, Ask, Bing, AltaVista, and Google Scholar compared to their female counterparts, resulting in better job performance.

This finding aligns with Ekenna and Mabawonku (2013), who emphasized that strategic retrieval skills play a crucial role in improving search proficiency and enhancing the utilization of online information resources. Additionally, it corroborates the study by Chu and Law (2008), which found that improved strategic search skills accelerate the information retrieval process, contribute to more effective and comprehensive searches, and enhance the utilization of online information resources.

The findings of this study align with those of Roy and Chi (2013), who investigated the impact of gender and age on performing complex search tasks. Their study found that boys and girls employed different search strategies. Specifically, boys spent more time formulating queries and scanning search engine results pages (horizontal search), whereas girls, upon clicking search results, engaged in deeper browsing and thoroughly examined entire websites (vertical search).

Similarly, the findings of this study are consistent with those of Large et al. (2012), who observed gender-based differences in search behavior among 11-year-old children. Their research found that boys frequently used single-keyword searches, while girls were more likely to combine multiple keywords. Additionally, boys clicked on links more frequently and spent less time on individual pages compared to girls. However, despite these behavioral differences, the actual search outcomes did not show significant variations between boys and girls.

In contrast, studies by Hargittai and Shafer (2006), Deursen and Dijk (2011), and Kuhlemeier and Hemker (2007), which employed actual performance tests, found no significant differences between men and women in online search proficiency. These contradictory findings suggest that gender differences in search strategies may exist in certain contexts but do not necessarily translate into significant disparities in search performance outcomes.

Summary

This study was driven by the need to determine whether gender differences in strategic online search skills, as widely reported in the literature, are also evident among male and female academics in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. The study population comprised 7,107 male and female academics across the seven federal universities in the region during the 2022/2023 academic session. A sample size of 1,393 participants was selected from this population using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Sample Size Determination Table.

To address the study's objectives, research questions were formulated, and research hypotheses were tested using means and standard deviation for descriptive analysis and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for inferential analysis. The findings revealed that six null hypotheses were rejected, while one was accepted. This indicates that a significant difference exists in job performance between male and female academics in federal universities in South-South Nigeria based on strategic online search skills.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that **male and female academics in federal universities in South-South Nigeria differ in job performance based on their strategic online search skills**. The results indicate that **male academics who acquire strategic online search skills demonstrate higher job performance compared to their female counterparts** in federal universities in the region.

Educational Implications of Findings

The findings of this study present several educational implications, including:

- a. **Gender differences in online resource utilization** – Men and women may exhibit distinct patterns in their use of online resources. Understanding these patterns can inform targeted interventions to bridge existing gaps in digital proficiency.
- b. **Impact on job performance** – The variations in job performance between male and female academics due to differences in online search skills highlight the need for female academics to leverage these skills to enhance their professional efficiency.
- c. **Addressing gender-specific barriers** – Identifying obstacles such as social expectations and time constraints can help shape policies that promote equal opportunities for skill acquisition across genders.
- d. **Encouraging female academics** – Institutions should actively encourage female academics to adopt online search skills at the same level as their male counterparts. Organizing seminars and workshops on ICT for both male and female lecturers can increase awareness of the academic potential of online search tools, fostering adaptability to evolving academic demands.
- e. **Promoting equitable academic environments** – Recognizing the intersection of gender, online search skills, and job performance is essential for fostering an inclusive and equitable academic environment, ultimately contributing to improved institutional outcomes.

Contributions to Knowledge

This study has contributed to knowledge by examining gender differences in the job performance of academics based on their online search skills in federal universities. The findings provide empirical data that can either support or challenge existing claims on this subject. Furthermore, the study offers valuable insights into the common practice in Nigerian universities, where gender is often considered a significant factor in recruitment decisions, training opportunities, educational advancement, capacity building in ICT, and overall job performance.

For instance, there is a notable underrepresentation of female lecturers at senior academic levels in many Nigerian universities. A prevailing argument is that some female academics prioritize teaching over other professional responsibilities, such as research, which is a critical requirement for promotion. This study provides empirical evidence that helps explain gender disparities and sheds light on the underlying factors contributing to gender inequality in Nigerian academia.

Additionally, this research paves the way for future studies by highlighting other

relevant variables such as age, educational qualifications, and academic rank that may influence job performance. As a result, this study will serve as a valuable reference material for prospective researchers and provide a foundation for further investigations aimed at fostering innovations in education and promoting gender inclusivity in academic institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. **Training and Capacity Building** – Universities should provide equal opportunities for both male and female academics through training, retraining, seminars, and workshops to enhance their online search skills, particularly strategic online search skills, thereby improving their job performance.
- ii. **Access to Research Funding and Incentives** – University management should expand access to research scholarships, funding opportunities, and grants, particularly for female academics. Considering their domestic responsibilities, certain waivers or flexible funding policies should be introduced to enhance their job performance through strategic online search skills.
- iii. **Addressing Gender-Specific Challenges** – The federal government and university management should take measures to minimize the challenges faced by female academics in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. Universities should implement gender-sensitive training programs on online search skills, ensuring equitable access to digital resources for all academics.
- iv. **Prioritizing Staff Development** – University management should place greater emphasis on staff development initiatives, particularly those aimed at encouraging female academics to engage in continuous professional growth and skill acquisition.

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